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**International Journal on Cybernetics &
Informatics (IJCI)**

ISSN : 2277 - 548X (Online) ; 2320 - 8430 (Print)

<http://airccse.org/journal/ijci/index.html>

FUTURE TRENDS IN FIBER OPTICS COMMUNICATION

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ABSTRACT

Fiber optic systems are vital media transmission foundation for overall broadband systems. Wide data transfer capacity (bandwidth) signal transmission with low delay is a key prerequisite in present day applications. Optical fiber give broad and incomparable transmission transfer speed with insignificant expectations, and are currently the transmission medium of decision for long separation and high information rate transmission in media transmission systems. This paper gives a review of fiber optic communication system, including their key advances, and furthermore talks about their mechanical pattern towards the next generation.

KEYWORDS

Bandwidth, Broadband, Fiber optics, Latency, Telecommunication

SOURCE URL : <http://airconline.com/ijci/V6N2/6217ijci03.pdf>

VOLUME LINK : <http://aircse.org/journal/ijci/Current2017.html>

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PREDICTING BANKRUPTCY USING MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS

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ABSTRACT

This paper is written for predicting Bankruptcy using different Machine Learning Algorithms. Whether the company will go bankrupt or not is one of the most challenging and toughest question to answer in the 21st Century. Bankruptcy is defined as the final stage of failure for a firm. A company declares that it has gone bankrupt when at that present moment it does not have enough funds to pay the creditors. It is a global problem. This paper provides a unique methodology to classify companies as bankrupt or healthy by applying predictive analytics. The prediction model stated in this paper yields better accuracy with standard parameters used for bankruptcy prediction than previously applied prediction methodologies.

KEYWORDS

Machine Learning, Classification, Regression, Correlation, Error Matrix, ROC

SOURCE URL : <http://airconline.com/ijci/V5N1/5116ijci10.pdf>

VOLUME LINK : <http://airccse.org/journal/ijci/Current2016.html>

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NFC: ADVANTAGES, LIMITS AND FUTURE SCOPE

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ABSTRACT

Near Field Communication (NFC) Technology represents short range (practically up to 4 cm) wireless communication offering safe yet simple and intuitive communication between electronic devices that we use on a daily basis. Users of devices having NFC application in it can simply touch their devices to other similar elements having NFC application to communicate with them, making application and data usage easy and convenient. NFC can be called as the next generation of Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) as technically its working principal is based on RFID however from application point of view it is similar to Bluetooth in some ways since it allows communication between two active devices. NFC can be the future medium of contactless electronic payment as it inhibits eavesdropping on NFC - enabled transactions pertaining to its short range, however range can be extended by attackers using some range extension system. In this paper we briefly discussed the advantages, limits or challenges of NFC technology along with its applications which opens up exciting new usage scenarios for mobile devices.

KEYWORDS

Near Field Communication, NFC, RFID, Bluetooth, Contactless communication

SOURCE URL : <http://airccse.org/journal/ijci/papers/4415ijci01.pdf>

VOLUME LINK : <http://airccse.org/journal/ijci/Current2015.html>

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TALENT MANAGEMENT IN EDUCATION SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

Attract, develop and retain employees by assured pipeline of knowledgeable and qualifying people is important for the success of the institutions which is known as talent management. The main issues facing by the educational institutes is shortage of competent and qualified faculties. It has resulted in institutions focusing on how to retain the talent and how to develop them. Where institutions are running at risk of talent crisis talent retention is the not only the choice of the managers but also the need for the institutions. The important factors which contributes to faculty retention and recruitment are benefits, supportive environments, spouse employment opportunities, start-up and resources and salaries. This research paper provides few strategies which institutions can adopt for attracting and retaining talent which is best available for them.

KEYWORDS

Talent Retention, Talent Acquisition and Talent Development, Education Sector, Strategies.

SOURCE URL : <http://airconline.com/ijci/V6N2/6217ijci06.pdf>

VOLUME LINK : <http://airccse.org/journal/ijci/Current2017.html>

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NEAR FIELD COMMUNICATION (NFC) TECHNOLOGY: A SURVEY

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ABSTRACT

Near Field Communication, NFC- is one of the latest short range wireless communication technologies. NFC provides safe communication between electronic gadgets. NFC-enabled devices can just be pointed or touched by the users of their devices to other NFC-enabled devices to communicate with them. With NFC technology, communication is established when an NFC-compatible device is brought within a few centimetres of another i.e. around 20 cm theoretically (4cm is practical). The immense benefit of the short transmission range is that it prevents eavesdropping on NFC-enabled dealings. NFC technology enables several innovative usage scenarios for mobile devices. NFC technology works on the basis of RFID technology which uses magnetic field induction to commence communication between electronic devices in close vicinity. NFC operates at 13.56MHz and has 424kbps maximum data transfer rate. NFC is complementary to Bluetooth and 802.11 with their long distance capabilities. In card emulation mode NFC devices can offer contactless/wireless smart card standard. This technology enables smart phones to replace traditional plastic cards for the purpose of ticketing, payment, etc. Sharing (share files between phones), service discovery i.e. get information by touching smart phones etc. are other possible applications of NFC using smart phones. This paper provides an overview of NFC technology in a detailed manner including working principle, transmission details, protocols and standards, application scenarios, future market, security standards and vendor's chipsets which are available for this standard. This comprehensive survey should serve as a useful guide for students, researchers and academicians who are interested in NFC Technology and its applications [1].

KEYWORDS

Near Field Communication, RFID

SOURCE URL : <http://airccse.org/journal/ijci/papers/4215ijci13.pdf>

VOLUME LINK : <http://airccse.org/journal/ijci/Current2015.html>

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